

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Pigmentation and awning patterns of summer rice cultivars in Assam

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A wide range of variability occurs in characters of traditional summer (ahu) rice varieties. Classification on the basis of pigment distribution is useful documentation for identifying the germplasm. We mapped pigmentation patterns of four floral parts—sterile lemmas, lemma and palea, apiculus, and stigma—and the awning patterns of 797 cultivars.

Table 1. Distribution of pigment in 4 floral parts of summer traditional varieties of Assam, India.

Color	Floral parts (no.)			
	Lemma and palea	Sterile lemma	Apiculus	Stigma
No pigmentation (straw)	507	780	685	559
Brown	34	—	—	—
Deep brown	9	—	—	—
Brown spots on straw	8	—	—	—
Brown furrows on straw	6	—	—	—
Purple	11	17	71	238
Light purple	5	—	34	—
Black	217	—	7	—
Total	797	797	797	797

Nonpigmented organs were more frequent. Some variation in coloration was observed, and it was highest in the lemma and palea (flowering glumes), followed by the apiculus (Table 1). Awning patterns are presented in Table 2. □

Table 2. Awning patterns of the summer traditional varieties of Assam, India.

Type	Frequency (no.)
Awn absent	515
Short, partly awned	108
Short, fully awned	30
Long, partly awned	113
Long, fully awned	11
Total	797

Genetics

Studies on blast (BI) resistance genes in indica rice

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Work on the genetics of resistance to rice BI disease caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. has identified 13 resistance genes. In general, a single dominant or two duplicate dominant genes govern resistance; in some cases, recessive genes and interactions of genes and gene linkage are found.

We studied the resistance genes for Chinese BI fungus races ZC3 and ZG1

in 10 indica rice cultivars. F₁, F₂, and B₁F₁ plants from crosses of susceptible (S)/resistant (R) cultivars and R/R cultivars were inoculated with the B1 races.

The results indicate that in these cultivars, a single dominant or two duplicate dominant genes govern resistance (see table). Eleven dominant genes (*P-1* to *P-11*) were found. When the same plants were inoculated with both races, some genes did not segregate independently. Parental types were more frequent than recombinant types. This result indicates that some resistance genes are linked (e.g., *P-1* and *P-6* in Tetep).

The results also show that expression of resistance might be affected by some modifier genes or that there might be multiple alleles confirming

different levels of resistance at the same locus. If more races were used, more resistance genes would be identified. Inheritance analysis of rice BI resistance could be done easily and effectively, using only a few common fungus races. □

Genetic studies of the F₂ and F₃ of tall × semidwarf rice varieties

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We evaluated several genetic variables in F₂ and F₃ of three crosses involving

Genes for resistance to 2 rice BI races in 10 cultivars. Hangzhou, China.

Race	Resistance gene in each cultivar									
	Tetep	Chai-tang	Ai-mei-zao 3	IR36	IR58	Suweon 300	Hong-yang-ai 4	Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi	IR9782	Guo-ji-you-zha
ZC3	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1, P-2</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1, P-2</i>	<i>P-3</i>	<i>P-4, P-5</i>
ZG1	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-8</i>	<i>P-9</i>	<i>P-6, P-7</i>	<i>P-6, P-7</i>	<i>P-7</i>	<i>P-8</i>	<i>P-14, P-11</i>

tall indica variety ASD1 and semidwarf varieties Co 33, ADT36, and IR50 (Table 1). Phenotypic correlations were computed between single-plant yield and yield components.

In the F₂, phenotypic and genotypic variability were high for tiller numbers, grains/panicle, and plant yield; low for days to panicle emergence and 100-grain weight; and moderate for plant height. In the F₃, variability was moderate for single-plant yield and low for other traits.

Additive gene action had more influence than environment on the traits. Days to panicle emergence had high broad-sense heritability with low genotypic coefficient of variability and

genetic advance in both generations, indicating nonadditive gene action. Changes between generations might be due to changes in gene frequency resulting from selection.

Correlations of number of productive tillers, harvest index, and dry matter production with single-plant yield were highly significant and positive for the F₂ and F₃ of almost all crosses (Table 2). These results indicate that high yielding ability might be associated with these three yield components.

Among the yield components, there was close positive association between panicle length and grain numbers/panicle. Grain number also correlated

positively with harvest index and dry matter production, indicating its importance in rice improvement.

The difference in direction and magnitude of correlations might be attributed to differences in gene association in the parental lines. The change in direction between F₂ and F₃ might be due to differential segregation and recombination.

In a path coefficient analysis of the direct and indirect effects on yield of nine characters, total correlation of dry matter production, harvest index, and number of productive tillers (except in the F₃ of ASD1/Co 33 and ASD1/DR50) with single-plant yield was highly significant in the F₂ and F₃ (Table 3).

Table 1. Genetic parameters of the F₂ and F₃ of tall/semidwarf crosses in Tamil Nadu.

Character	Cross	Generation	Mean	SD	PCV ^a	GCV ^b	h ^{2c}	GA ^d	GA (% of mean)
Days to panicle emergence	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	83.6	4.0	4.8	4.4	83.9	6.9	8.3
		F ₃	80.2	1.6	1.9	1.7	79.2	2.5	3.1
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	86.9	3.5	4.1	3.5	72.9	5.3	6.1
		F ₃	78.9	1.6	2.1	1.9	83.0	2.8	3.5
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	86.1	3.5	4.1	3.6	77.6	5.6	6.5
		F ₃	78.6	1.4	1.8	1.6	80.4	2.3	3.0
Plant height (cm)	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	102.3	15.2	14.8	13.6	84.1	26.1	25.5
		F ₃	109.6	12.0	11.0	10.9	98.4	24.4	22.2
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	116.9	15.6	13.4	12.2	83.0	26.7	22.8
		F ₃	105.3	12.0	11.4	11.4	98.6	24.5	23.2
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	106.5	15.3	14.3	13.1	83.4	26.2	24.6
		F ₃	112.2	7.8	7.0	6.8	96.6	15.5	13.8
Number of productive tillers	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	8.6	4.0	45.8	33.9	54.6	4.5	51.6
		F ₃	6.3	0.7	11.3	8.0	52.7	0.8	12.0
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	7.9	3.7	46.7	36.5	61.3	4.7	59.0
		F ₃	7.4	0.9	12.1	10.3	73.1	1.3	18.2
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	9.2	3.9	41.7	31.7	57.7	4.6	57.9
		F ₃	8.0	0.9	10.7	8.5	63.6	1.1	14.0
Panicle length (cm)	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	22.3	2.9	13.0	10.6	66.9	4.0	17.9
		F ₃	22.8	0.9	4.1	3.2	61.6	1.2	5.2
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	23.5	2.4	10.4	7.9	56.2	2.9	12.4
		F ₃	22.4	0.9	4.0	2.5	40.0	0.7	3.3
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	22.8	2.7	11.8	9.7	68.0	3.8	16.5
		F ₃	22.2	0.8	3.4	1.9	30.0	0.5	2.1
Grain no./panicle	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	90.2	34.5	40.0	32.6	66.5	49.4	54.8
		F ₃	104.8	9.3	8.9	8.3	86.1	16.5	15.8
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	87.7	27.8	31.7	21.4	45.7	26.2	29.8
		F ₃	87.0	7.6	8.7	7.8	80.0	12.4	14.3
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	83.7	30.2	36.1	26.0	51.9	32.3	37.6
		F ₃	92.0	9.8	10.6	9.9	87.2	17.6	19.1
100-grain weight	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	2.3	0.3	11.3	9.7	74.4	0.4	17.3
		F ₃	2.3	0.3	11.9	11.4	91.5	0.5	22.4
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	2.4	0.2	8.6	7.1	66.8	0.3	11.9
		F ₃	2.4	0.1	5.6	4.0	51.2	0.1	5.9
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	2.5	0.2	8.8	6.9	62.4	0.3	11.3
		F ₃	2.3	0.2	6.7	5.5	68.4	0.2	9.4
Single-plant yield	ASD1/Co 33	F ₂	12.4	6.0	48.1	41.2	73.3	9.0	72.7
		F ₃	10.2	1.9	18.3	15.2	69.1	2.7	26.0
	ASD1/ADT36	F ₂	12.5	6.3	50.6	41.9	68.6	8.9	71.5
		F ₃	9.7	1.3	13.0	9.8	56.3	1.5	15.1
	ASD1/IR50	F ₂	13.8	6.6	47.9	36.7	58.6	8.0	57.8
		F ₃	9.1	1.8	19.4	16.6	72.9	2.6	29.2

^aPhenotypic coefficient of variability. ^bGenotypic coefficient of variability. ^cBroad-sense heritability. ^dGenetic advance.

Table 2. Phenotypic correlations between yield and yield components in F₂ and F₃ of tall/semidwarf rice crosses in Tamil Nadu.

Character	Cross	Plant height		Number of productive tillers		Panicle length		Grain no./panicle		100-grain weight		Harvest index		Dry matter production		Single-plant yield	
		F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃
		Days to panicle emergence	ASD1/Co 33	-0.16	-0.01	-0.38*	-0.06	-0.09	-0.01	0.16	-0.26	-0.26	0.11	-0.08	-0.09	-0.08	0.09
	ASD1/ADT36	0.11	-0.04	0.26	0.46*	0.01	0.09	-0.10	-0.03	-0.04	0.40*	0.14	0.13	0.27	0.13	0.29	0.24
	ASD1/IR50	-0.17	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.14	0.04	0.03	-0.01	0.10	0.39*	0.02	0.20	0.11	-0.05	0.10	0.09
Plant height	ASD1/Co33			0.04	0.25	0.18	0.23	-0.06	0.32	0.18	0.11	-0.06	-0.07	0.09	0.57**	0.08	0.35
	ASD1/ADT36			-0.30	0.01	0.17	0.28	-0.29	0.31	-0.05	0.22	-0.16	0.01	-0.28	0.21	0.30	0.21
	ASD1/IR50			-0.05	-0.10	0.17	0.29	-0.24	0.46*	-0.15	0.01	-0.08	0.44*	0.03	0.83**	-0.01	0.89**
Number of productive tillers	ASD1/Co33					0.22	0.07	0.19	0.40**	0.29	-0.05	0.48*	0.11	0.37*	0.24	0.48**	0.25
	ASD1/ADT36					0.36	-0.02	0.28	-0.07	0.06	0.32	0.46*	-0.08	0.93**	0.49**	0.96**	0.38*
	ASD1/IR50					0.27	-0.17	0.46*	0.09	0.01	-0.16	0.44*	0.10	0.83**	0.31	0.89**	0.30
Panicle length	ASD1/Co 33							0.17	0.43*	0.32	-0.02	0.21	0.05	-0.18	0.42*	-0.09	0.33
	ASD1/ADT36							0.13	0.45*	-0.30	0.08	0.13	-0.20	0.37*	0.24	0.36*	0.03
	ASD1/IR50							0.26	0.04	-0.30	0.08	0.02	-0.23	0.25	-0.14	0.25	-0.29
Grain no./panicle	ASD1/Co33									0.13	-0.17	0.23	0.02	0.32	0.44*	0.29	0.32
	ASD1/ADT36									0.22	0.15	0.21	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.18	0.15
	ASD1/IR50									-0.19	-0.04	0.33	0.13	0.39*	0.19	0.40*	0.21
100-grain weight	ASD1/Co 33											0.12	-0.12	0.13	0.08	0.20	-0.03
	ASD1/ADT36											0.13	0.24	0.07	0.04	0.07	0.28
	ASD1/IR50											0.11	-0.02	-0.03	0.01	0.01	-0.03
Harvest index	ASD1/Co 33													0.46*	-0.01	0.61**	0.70**
	ASD1/ADT36													0.31	-0.35	0.54**	0.54**
	ASD1/IR50													0.24	0.04	0.48**	0.70**
Dry matter production	ASD1/Co 33															0.96**	0.71**
	ASD1/ADT36															0.96**	0.59**
	ASD1/IR50															0.95**	0.73**

*Significant at 5% level. **Significant at 1% level.

Dry matter production made the highest contribution to the yield, with a high positive direct effect in both generations of all crosses. The indirect effect of dry matter production via harvest index was positive except in F₃ of ASD1/ADT36 and ASD1/Co 33.

The direct effect of harvest index on single plant yield ranged from moderate to high in both generations. Harvest index showed a moderate to high-positive indirect effect via dry matter production. □

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Table 3. Direct effect and indirect effect of yield components on single-plant yield through harvest index and dry matter production in F₂ and F₃ of tall/semidwarf rice crosses. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986-87.

Characters	Cross	Direct effect		Indirect effect				Phenotypic correlation value with single-plant yield	
		F ₂	F ₃	Harvest index		Dry matter production		F ₂	F ₃
				F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃		
Harvest index	ASD1/Co 33	0.18	0.70	--	--	0.40	-0.01	0.61**	0.70**
	ASD1/ADT36	0.25	0.84	--	--	0.27	-0.31	0.54**	0.54**
	ASD1/IR50	0.24	0.68	--	--	0.19	0.03	0.48**	0.70**
Dry matter production	ASD1/Co 33	0.87	0.73	0.08	-0.01	--	--	0.96**	0.71**
	ASD1/ADT36	0.86	0.88	0.08	-0.30	--	--	0.96**	0.59**
	ASD1/IR50	0.77	0.70	0.06	0.02	--	--	0.95**	0.73**
Days to panicle emergence	ASD1/Co 33	0.08	-0.01	0.01	-0.06	-0.07	0.07	-0.07	-0.01
	ASD1/ADT36	0.02	-0.01	0.03	0.11	0.24	0.12	0.29	0.24
	ASD1/IR50	0.01	-0.01	0.01	0.14	0.08	-0.03	0.10	0.09
Plant height	ASD1/Co 33	-0.01	-0.02	-0.01	-0.05	0.08	0.42	0.08	0.35
	ASD1/ADT36	-0.01	0.01	-0.04	0.01	-0.24	0.19	-0.30	0.21
	ASD1/IR50	0.01	0.03	-0.06	-0.05	0.12	0.02	0.06	-0.01
Number of productive tillers	ASD1/Co 33	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.08	0.32	0.17	0.48**	0.25
	ASD1/ADT36	0.01	0.01	0.12	-0.07	0.80	0.43	0.95**	0.38*
	ASD1/IR50	0.16	0.02	0.11	0.07	0.64	0.22	0.89**	0.30
Panicle length	ASD1/Co 33	-0.01	-0.01	0.04	0.04	-0.15	0.31	-0.09	0.33
	ASD1/ADT36	-0.01	-0.03	0.03	-0.17	0.31	0.21	0.36*	0.03
	ASD1/IR50	0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.19	0.19	-0.10	0.25	-0.29

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Table 3 continued

Characters	Cross	Direct effect		Indirect effect				Phenotypic correlation value with single-plant yield		
		F ₂	F ₃	Harvest index		Dry matter production		F ₂	F ₃	
				F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃			
Grain no./panicle	ASD1/Co 33	-0.07	-0.01	0.04	0.01	0.28	0.32	0.29	0.32	
	ASD1/ADT36	0.06	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.15	
	ASD1/IR50	-0.06	0.01	0.08	0.09	0.30	0.13	0.40**	0.21	
100-grain weight	ASD1/Co 33	0.08	-0.01	0.02	-0.08	0.11	0.06	0.20	-0.03	
	ASD1/ADT36	-0.03	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.27	
	ASD1/IR50	-0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.03	
Residual effect		F ₂	F ₃							
		ASD1/Co 33	0.16	0.06						
		ASD1/ADT36	0.12	0.09						
		ASD1/IR50	0.17	0.07						

**Significant at the 1% level. *Significant at 5% level.

Near-isogenic pairs of indica rices with blast (BI) resistance genes

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Rice BI-resistant near-isogenic pairs involving resistant lines with different genes and corresponding susceptible lines facilitate systematic genetic analysis and molecular study of BI re-

sistance. Each pair has a highly uniform genetic background; they presumably differ only in the resistance genes.

We crossed resistant cultivars Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi, Tetep, and IR58 with the susceptible recurrent parent Zhen-shan 97. Plants segregating for resistance to Chinese BI races ZB15 and ZC15 were selected for successive selfing generations to produce resistant and susceptible lines (see figure). Reactions to Chinese BI races ZB15,

Reaction of near-isogenic pairs to 3 Chinese rice BI fungus races. Hangzhou, China.

Isogenic pairs	Resistance donor	Reaction ^a		
		ZB15	ZC15	ZF1
H1 R and H5 R	Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi	R	R	S
H1 S and H5 S		S	S	S
H2 R and H3 R		R	R	R
H2 S and H3 S		S	S	S
H4 R and H6 R		R	R	R
H4 S and H6 S		S	S	R
H7 R	Tetep	R	R	R
H7 S		S	S	S
H8 R	IR58	R	R	R
H8 S		S	S	R
H9 R		R	R	S
H9 S		S	S	R
H10 R		S	R	R
H10 S		S	S	S

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible.

ZC15, and ZF1 of 10 near-isogenic pairs differed (see table).

Studies on the molecular biology of rice BI resistance are under way using the pairs. □

Procedure for selecting near-isogenic pair H1 R and H1 S. Lines were backcrossed three times then BC₃ plants were selfed 9 times to produce BC₃F₁₀R and S lines. Selection of other pairs was similar. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Breeding methods

Anther culturability of rice lines bearing cytoplasmic male sterility

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An increase of anther culturability in cytoplasmic male sterile lines relative to male fertile varieties has been reported in wheat and tobacco. We did a similar study in rice.

The wild abortive cytoplasm (WA), which usually promotes microspore abortion at the uninucleate stage, and the Chinsurah Boro II cytoplasm (BT), which usually triggers a late degeneration of the pollen grains between the binucleated and trinucleated stage, were introduced by successive backcrosses into upland rice varieties IRAT313, IRAT103, and IRAT177.

Cytological observations showed apparently identical aspects of the